

The Impact of Information Organization and Management in the 21st Century: A Case Study of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt, Nigeria.

Victor WAGWU PhD (CLN)

Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuorlumeni,
Port-Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria.

vwagwu@gmail.com

Angela Ebele OKPALA PhD (CLN)

National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) Abuja, Nigeria.

aokpala@noun.edu.ng

Abstract

The study examined the structure and management of information in the twenty-first century. Specifically, it looked into the connections between information management and bibliographic control, abstracting and information management in this period, and classification and information management. To direct the investigation, the researchers developed three research questions and hypotheses. The Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Library in Port Harcourt, Nigeria, which was researched in its totality owing to its modest size, has 32 staff members. A correctional research design was used for this study. A structured questionnaire was employed as the study tool. The developed hypotheses were tested using the t-test, and descriptive statistics, including frequency counts, means, and standard deviations, were used in the data analysis process. The findings revealed significant relationships between classification and information management, bibliographic control and information management, and abstracting and information management in the 21st century. Consequently, the study recommended resource centres should prioritise information organisation such as classification and bibliographic control in information organisation.

Keywords: Information, information organisation, information management, University libraries

Introduction

Information is essential for reducing uncertainty in research and development (Pujar, 2007, as cited in Vijayakumar, 2011). Information is the output that results from analyzing, contextualizing, structuring, interpreting or processing data. Information infuses meaning and value into the data, facilitates understanding, communication and learning, and is a key factor in system designs and strategic planning, as well as in problem-solving and decision-making. Choo (1998) describes "information management as a cycle of processes that support the organisation learning activities: identifying information needs, acquiring information, organising and storing information, developing information products and services, distributing information, and using information". Knowledge, concepts, information, facts, and creative works conveyed either formally or informally are all included in Information Organization (Chen and Hernon, n.d., as cited in Vijayakumar, 2011). Quora (2022) said information organisation is structuring and arranging data or knowledge systematically and meaningfully

to facilitate understanding, retrieval and use in order to save the time of librarians and users. Information organisation is an intellectual discipline concerned with activities such as document description, indexing, abstraction and classification that provide systems of representation and order for knowledge and information (Joudrey et al., 2018).

Atanda and Adeyemi (2018), a classification scheme is a framework for grouping all of human knowledge into broad domains and specific issues. Classification schemes are primarily used to help librarians organise knowledge so that books may be found and retrieved in designated locations with ease. Classification systems can be divided into the following types depending on how they are used: Universal schemes to cover all subjects, the Dewey Decimal Classification (DDC), Universal Decimal Classification (UDC), Library of Congress Classification (LCC), and Colon Classification (CC). Ashikuzzaman (2024) said abstracting services are specialised solutions that are pivotal in distilling and summarising complex information from various sources. It aims to extract the essence of content, condensing it into a concise and understandable form without compromising its essential meaning. Bibliographies are beneficial to researchers and advanced students since they make it easier to find previously published works in their subjects and help identify and select pertinent information. Amaraweera, (2010) said bibliography is an essential resource for library information retrieval. It is a list of articles, books, or shorter works that can be used to locate sources of information

Statement of the Problem

Organisations have amassed enormous volumes of data from numerous departments and outside sources recently. Organising this abundance of data is essential for more productive decision-making. However, managing such vast amounts of heterogeneous data presents formidable obstacles that call for effective and flexible administration. It was observed that inefficient information and record administration is a problem in many institutions. This inefficiency causes problems with finding and deleting outdated material and makes it harder to access and retrieve pertinent information. There have also been reported cases of information loss. Additional issues that have been noted include redundant data, insufficient data security protocols, difficulties with data preservation, and barriers to data and information sharing between organisational divisions.

This study examines the effects of information organization and management in the twenty-first century in light of these difficulties. Its goal is to identify areas where current practices fall short and investigate strategies for improving the efficacy and efficiency of information management procedures within businesses.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study:

1. What is the relationship between classification and information management in the 21st century?
2. What is the significant relationship between bibliographic control and information management in the 21st century?

3. What is the significant relationship between abstracting and information management in the 21st century?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses, stated in a null form, guided the study:

- H₀₁:** There is no significant relationship between classification and information management in the 21st century.
- H₀₂:** There is no significant relationship between bibliographic control and information management in the 21st century.
- H₀₃:** There is no significant relationship between abstracting and information management in the 21st century.

Literature Review

It is impossible to overestimate the importance of information; it is a beacon of light for all academic fields. Vijayakumar (2011) emphasizes its significance, describing it as a basic resource essential for surviving in today's cutthroat and connected world.

Information Management

Information is essential for reducing uncertainty, research and development (Idachaba et al. 2021). Knowledge, concepts, information, facts, and creative works conveyed either formally or informally are all included in information organisation (Chen and HERNON, n.d., as cited in Vijayakumar, 2011). Information is priceless, especially for libraries where patrons need to acquire information quickly and easily (Uwaifo, 2006, as cited in Vijayakumar, 2011). Information is the output that results from analysing, contextualising, structuring, interpreting, or processing data in other ways. Information infuses meaning and value into the data. It facilitates understanding, communication, and learning and is a key factor in system designs and strategic planning, as well as problem-solving and decision-making. Information brings context to the data, turning what would otherwise be meaningless content into something understandable and usable. Information management is a complex work of acquiring, organising, preserving, collecting, circulating, and maintaining the printed or digital resources of knowledge (Rifaudeen, 2015). Information Management in Libraries Rowley (1998) proposes four different levels of information management: information retrieval, information systems, information contexts, and information environments. Effective information management needs to address issues at all of these levels.

Choo (1998) defines "information management as a cycle of processes that support the organisation learning activities: identifying information needs, acquiring information, organising and storing information, developing information products and services, distributing information, and using information" Radon,(1996) pinpoints the importance of Information

Management in Libraries even in the modern ICT environment as "the new technologies of the Internet and beyond will require more expertise in information management". Hence, information management plays a significant role in organising library information resources and services. Information organisation is a process of describing information sources and access points, making access to materials easy. According to Medhi (2013), information management is essential to success.

Information Organization

Information organisation is a process of describing information sources and access points, making easy access to materials to save the time of library patrons and librarians. Information organisation in the library is fundamentally for easy access and retrieval of information. Quora (2022) said information organisation is structuring and arranging data or knowledge in a systematic and meaningful way to facilitate understanding, retrieval and use to save the time of librarians and users. Information organisation is an intellectual discipline concerned with activities such as document description, indexing, and classification that provide systems of representation and order for knowledge and information. Information organisation is an intellectual discipline concerned with document description, indexing, abstraction and classification that provide systems of representation and order for knowledge and information (Joudrey et al., 2018).

Dimensions of Information Organisation Classification

The classification system used to organise library books is crucial for making it simple to locate and retrieve information resources from the shelves of libraries. According to Nnadozie (2007), referenced in Atanda and Adeyemi (2018), a classification scheme is a framework for grouping all human knowledge into broad domains and specific issues. Classification schemes are primarily used to help librarians organise knowledge so that books can be easily found and retrieved in designated locations. Books on the same subject would not be arranged together on the shelf or available as class numbers in indexes without classification schemes. Libraries utilise various classification techniques according to the size and kind of their collections. Classification schemes have been adapted for the organisation of electronic information resources, even though their initial purpose was to arrange bibliographic objects on actual library shelves. For example, BUBL LINK offers access to a catalogue of more than 11,000 carefully chosen online resources arranged using the Dewey Decimal Classification (DDC). The Dewey class (such as 300: Social Sciences) or a term or phrase from the alphabetical index can be used by users to search the catalogue. Customers can now access digital materials using subject-specific alphabetical or category listings (Atanda & Adeyemi, 2018).

Also, librarianship studies (2023) Library Classification system is the process of arranging, grouping, coding, and organising books and other library materials (e.g. serials, sound recordings, moving images, cartographic materials, manuscripts, computer files, e-resources etc.) on shelves or entries of a catalogue, bibliography, and index according to their subject in a systematic, logical, and helpful order by way of assigning them call numbers using a library classification system, so that users can find them as quickly and efficiently as possible. Mlinar (2021) opined that library classification is the arrangement of books on shelves, or description of them, in the manner which is most beneficial to users and librarians. He further stated that library classification is meant to achieve these four purposes: systematically ordering the fields of knowledge, bringing related items together in the most helpful sequence, providing orderly access on the shelf, and providing a location for an item

on the shelf. Nevertheless, classification systems can be divided into the following types depending on how they are used: Universal schemes to cover all subjects, the Dewey Decimal Classification (DDC), Universal Decimal Classification (UDC), Library of Congress Classification (LCC), and Colon Classification (CC).

Abstracting

A succinct overview of a document's contents is called an abstract; this is not the same as an extract, annotation, or summary (Lancaster, 2003, cited in Atanda & Adeyemi, 2018). It adheres to the original document's style and format and gives a succinct yet accurate summary of its key ideas (Rowley, 1996, cited in Atanda & Adeyemi, 2018). Abstracts may be a part of the original document or its substitute. Ashikuzzaman (2024) opined that abstracting services are indispensable pillars in information organisation, providing a crucial bridge between the overwhelming expanse of data and the quest for meaningful insights. He further that in this digital world abstracting services offer a vital solution to distill, categorise, and present complex data in a concise and accessible manner. These services act as intellectual filters, sifting through the noise to extract the essential elements, enabling users to grasp critical concepts without being overwhelmed by the sheer volume of information. From scholarly articles to business reports, abstracting services are fundamental in summarising content while preserving its substantive value.

Ashikuzzaman (2024) said abstracting services are specialised solutions that are pivotal in distilling and summarising complex information from various sources. These services aim to extract the essence of content, condensing it into a concise and understandable form without compromising its essential meaning. Abstracts, the condensed representations created by abstracting services, are efficient tools for users seeking a quick understanding of a particular topic, research paper, or document. Beyond mere summarization, abstracting involves a nuanced interpretation of the content, providing readers with a synthesised view that captures key ideas, findings, and arguments. Often employed in academic, scientific, and professional settings, abstracting services cater to individuals looking to navigate the vast sea of information more efficiently, making critical knowledge more accessible and digestible.

Bibliographic Control

Bibliographic control comprises creating, organising, managing and maintaining Bibliographic records to facilitate access to information. It includes standardising descriptions, subject access, creating catalogues and finding aids, and providing physical access (Amaraweera, 2010). A bibliography is an essential resource for information retrieval in libraries. It is a list of articles, books, or shorter works that can be used to locate sources of information. Finding more works by a particular author or works on specific subjects would be difficult without bibliographies. Reference librarians can direct users toward pertinent resources for their study topics thanks to the wide variety of bibliographies that have been prepared for various purposes. Bibliographies can also point to works that a particular library might not have. Authors usually cite their sources when compiling reference lists or bibliographies when writing a book or journal article. These materials are generally listed alphabetically by the author's surname, then additional names, the title, the publisher, the place and date of publication, and the total number of pages. The Modern Language Association (MLA) style is the name given to this arrangement type. The date is positioned right after the author's name in a different form called the Harvard style. Bibliographies are beneficial to researchers and advanced students since they make it easier to find previously published works in their subjects and help identify and select pertinent

information. It is advised to consult bibliographies when looking for literature on certain subjects because they offer helpful direction for obtaining the available material (Atanda & Adeyemi, 2018).

Empirical Framework

Several scholars have empirically investigated some areas of academics related to information organisation and management. This section will deal with the empirical research conducted by others.

Idachaba et al. (2021) conducted a study titled "Organization and Preservation of Government Publications at Benue State Legislative Library, Makurdi." Eleven (11) staff members made up the study's population, and total enumeration sampling was employed. Using a structured questionnaire as their tool, the researchers used SPSS to analyse the data and produce mean scores that addressed the study questions. According to the study, bibliographic services, indexing, abstracting, cataloguing, and classification were all part of organising government publications. On the other hand, it also noted difficulties such as restricted physical accessibility, budgetary limitations, absence of bibliographic control, various classification systems, adverse government regulations, and inadequate tools/materials. The study's recommendations were based on these findings, and they included the creation of programs for Selective Dissemination of Information (SDI) and Current Awareness Services (CAS), yearly budgetary allocations, improved bibliographic control, adoption of a single classification scheme, hiring qualified staff, creating efficient policies, and supplying sufficient supplies and equipment. The reviewed study is related to the current study in the area of content of organisation of information. However, the study differs from the current study in terms of population, location, design, and scope.

Muhammad et al. (2020) looked into the essential elements of implementing successful Information Governance (IG) frameworks in Nigerian universities in a different study. They conducted semi-structured interviews with eleven stakeholders in a university's records and information management using a case study methodology and a qualitative research approach. The software ATLAS-ti 7.0 was utilised by the researchers to analyse qualitative data. According to their findings, some essential elements are needed for the successful implementation of IG in university settings, including finance, stakeholder involvement, policy framework, a conducive atmosphere, human resources, and information and communication technologies (ICT). The reviewed study is related to the current study in the area of content of information governance. However, the study differs from the current study in population, location, design and scope.

The literature has shown the connection between information management, some factors and information organization from the literature reviewed so far, it is noticeable that none of the studies focused on information organization and management in IAUE. The study, therefore, sought to fill the gap.

Methodology

The study used a correlational approach to examine the effects of information organization and management in the twenty-first century. It was carried out among the thirty-two (32) staff members at the Main Library of the Ignatius Ajuru University of Education. Because of the manageable size of the population, the researchers chose a census approach that included every staff member. To collect data, a self-structured questionnaire with a 5-point Likert rating scale

(Strongly Agree = 5; Agree = 4; Undecided = 3; Disagree = 2; Strongly Disagree = 1) was used. It was named the "Influence of Information Organization and Information Management Questionnaire (INIOINMAQ)." To reduce data loss, the researcher personally gave the surveys to the respondents, and all completed forms were promptly gathered. The data was analysed using descriptive statistics, including means, standard deviations, and frequency counts. On a 5-point scale, mean scores of 3.0 or above were seen as markers of agreement, while those that were lower were regarded as indicators of disagreement. The study tested the hypotheses at a significance level of 0.05 using inferential statistics, especially the T-test.

Results

Question 1: What is the relationship between classification and information management in the 21st century?

Table 1. Responses on the Relationship between Classification and Information Management in the 21st Century

S/N	Item	Respondents/Responses					
		Females			Males		
		Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N
			\bar{X}				
1.	Classification makes the retrieval of books easy	4.92	0.28	24	4.37	0.52	8
2.	Classification makes accessing information resources easier	4.82	0.34	24	4.25	0.46	8
3.	Human knowledge is categorised through classification	4.83	0.44	24	4.25	0.46	8
4.	It helps the librarian to map the universe of knowledge	4.79	0.41	24	4.37	0.46	8
Grand Mean/SD		4.85	0.37	24	4.31	0.49	8

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Table 1 presents the findings related to job design as a dimension of stress management strategies, as indicated by responses to four research statements in the questionnaire. The table includes the mean score (\bar{x}), standard deviation (SD), and the population (N) for each group. The first research statement aimed to determine if classification in the respondents' organisation makes the retrieval of books easy. The mean score for this item was 4.59 with a standard deviation of 0.28 for females and 4.37 with a standard deviation of 0.52 for males, indicating a positive affirmation from both groups. The second research statement sought to assess whether classification in the organization makes accessing information resources easier. The mean score for this item was 4.82, with a standard deviation of 0.34 for males and 4.25, with a standard deviation of 0.46 for females, again indicating a positive affirmation from both groups.

The third research statement aimed to determine if human knowledge is categorised through classification in the organisation. The responses were also affirmative, with a mean score of

4.83 and a standard deviation of 0.44 for males and a mean score of 4.25 with a standard deviation of 0.46 for females. The fourth research statement sought to ascertain if classification helps the librarian map the knowledge universe. The responses were affirmative, with a mean score of 4.79 and a standard deviation of 0.41 for males and a mean score of 4.37 with a standard deviation of 0.46 for females.

Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship between classification and information management in the 21st century.

Table 2: T-test Analysis of Responses on the Significant Relationship between Classification and Information Organisation in the 21st Century.

Group	Mean \bar{X}	Std. Dev.	N	Df	Std. Error	P	T-cal. value	T-tab. value	Decision
Females	4.85	0.37	24	30	0.19	0.05	2.84	1.96	Ho Rejected
Males	4.31	0.49	8						

Field Survey, 2021

Table 2 presents the results of the hypothesis testing for the relationship between classification and information organisation in the 21st century. The calculated t-value is 2.84, while the critical t-table value is at a significance level of 0.05 and the degrees of freedom of 30 is 1.96. The null hypothesis is rejected since the calculated t-value (2.84) is greater than the critical t-table value (1.96). This result indicates a statistically significant relationship between classification and information organisation in the 21st century. This finding implies that classification is an essential information organisation in 21st-century libraries.

Question 2: What is the relationship between bibliographic control and information management in the 21st century?

Table 3. Responses on the Relationship between Bibliographic Control and Information Management in 21st Century

S/ N	Item	Respondents/Responses					
		Females			Males		
		Mean \bar{X}	SD	N	Mean \bar{X}	SD	N
1.	Bibliographic control is aimed at easy identification of information resources	4.92	0.28	24	4.37	0.52	8
2.	It is aimed at easy storage of information resources	4.87	0.34	24	4.25	0.46	8
3.	Easy retrieval of information resources is possible through bibliographic control	4.83	0.44	24	4.25	0.46	8
4.	It is easy to locate information resources through bibliographic control	4.79	0.41	24	4.37	0.52	8
5.	Easy collection of information resource is possible through bibliographic control	4.79	0.41	24	4.37	0.52	8
Grand Mean/SD		4.84	0.38	24	4.32	0.50	8

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Table 3 presents the results of the assessment of bibliographic control as a dimension of information organisation based on responses to five research statements in the questionnaire. The table includes the mean score (\bar{x}), standard deviation (SD), and the population (N) for each group. For the first statement, which aimed to ascertain whether bibliographic control in their organization facilitates the identification of information resources, the mean scores were 4.92 with a standard deviation of 0.28 for females and 4.37 with a standard deviation of 0.52 for males, indicating a positive affirmation. The second statement sought to determine if bibliographic control in their organisation is aimed at easy storage of information resources. The results showed a mean score (\bar{x}) of 4.83 with a standard deviation of 0.44 for females and 4.25 with a standard deviation of 0.46 for males, again indicating positive affirmation.

The third statement aimed to establish whether easy retrieval of information resources is possible through bibliographic control. The responses indicated affirmative, with mean scores (\bar{x}) of 4.83 and standard deviations of 0.44 for females and 4.25 and a standard deviation of 0.46 for males. The fourth statement sought to ascertain if it is easy to locate information resources through bibliographic control in their organisation. The responses also showed a positive affirmation with a mean score (\bar{x}) of 4.79 and a standard deviation of 0.41 for females, while for males, the mean score was 4.37 with a standard deviation of 0.52. Finally, the fifth statement aimed to determine whether easy collection of information resources is possible through bibliographic control in their organization. The responses again indicated a positive affirmation, with a mean score (\bar{x}) of 4.79 and a standard deviation of 0.41 for females and a mean score of 4.37 and a standard deviation of 0.52 for males. Overall, Table 3 shows that the respondents agreed on all items of bibliographic control as a dimension of information organisation, with a mean score greater than 3.0, indicating a substantial and adequate level of affirmation. The implication of this finding is that bibliographic control is indispensable information organization in 21st-century libraries.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant relationship between bibliographic control and information management in the 21st century.

Table 4: T-test Analysis of Responses on the Significant Relationship between Bibliographic Control and Information Management in 21st Century.

Group	Mean \bar{X}	Std. Dev.	N	Df	Std. Error	P	T-cal. value	T-tab. value	Decision
Females	4.84	0.38	24	30	0.19	0.05	2.74	1.96	Ho Rejected
Males	4.32	0.50	8						

Field Survey, 2021

Table 4 presents the results of the T-test analysis to determine the relationship between bibliographic control and information management in the 21st century. The table includes the calculated T-value, the T-table value, the alpha level of significance ($P < 0.05$), and the degree of freedom (30).

The calculated T-value is 2.74, which is higher than the T-table value of 1.96. Since the calculated T-value exceeds the critical T-value at the 0.05 significance level, the null hypothesis is rejected. This indicates that there is a significant relationship between bibliographic control and information management in the 21st century. From this finding bibliographic control is needed information organization in the 21st century libraries.

Question 3. What is the relationship between abstracting and information management in the 21st century?

Table 5: Responses on the Relationship between Abstracting and Information Management in 21st Century

S/No.	Item	Respondents/Responses					
		Females			Males		
		Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N
			\bar{X}				
1.	Abstracting carries the objectives as contained in a document	4.79	0.41	24	4.37	0.52	8
2.	It also contains the scope as contained in a document	4.87	0.34	24	4.25	0.46	8
3.	The procedure, as contained in a document, is also considered in abstracting	4.79	0.41	24	4.37	0.52	8
4.	Methodology, as contained in a document, is also considered in abstracting	4.79	0.41	24	4.37	0.52	8
5.	Conclusion, as contained in a document, is also included in abstracting	4.79	0.41	24	4.37	0.52	8
Grand Mean/SD		4.81	0.40	24	4.35	0.51	24

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Table 5 presents the results of abstracting as a dimension of information organization based on responses to five research statements in the questionnaire. The table includes the mean score (\bar{x}), standard deviation (SD), and the population (N) for each group (females and males). The first item aimed to ascertain if abstracting in their organisation carries the objectives of a document. The mean score (\bar{x}) was 4.79 with a standard deviation of 0.41 for females and 4.37 with a standard deviation of 0.52 for males, indicating a positive affirmation by both groups. The second item sought to determine if abstracting also includes the scope as contained in a document. The mean score (\bar{x}) was 4.87 with a standard deviation of 0.34 for females and 4.25 with a standard deviation of 0.46 for males, again showing a positive affirmation by both groups—the third item aimed to establish if the procedure as contained in a document is considered in abstracting. The mean score (\bar{x}) was 4.79 with a standard deviation of 0.41 for females and 4.37 with a standard deviation of 0.52 for males, indicating a positive affirmation by both groups. The fourth statement sought to ascertain if the methodology as contained in a document is considered in abstracting. The mean score (\bar{x}) was 4.79 with a standard deviation of 0.41 for females and 4.37 with a standard deviation of 0.52 for males, once again showing a positive affirmation by both groups. Finally, the fifth statement aimed to determine if the conclusion contained in a document is inclusive in abstracting. The mean score (\bar{x}) was 4.79

with a standard deviation of 0.41 for females and 4.37 with a standard deviation of 0.52 for males, indicating a positive affirmation by both groups.

Overall, Table 5 shows that respondents from both groups agreed on all items of abstracting as a dimension of information organization, with a mean score > 3.0 , indicating that both groups affirm that abstracting is related to information organization in libraries. This finding implies that abstracting is requisite in information organization in 21st-century libraries.

Hypothesis Three: There is no significant relationship between abstracting and information management in the 21st century.

Table 6: T-test Analysis of Responses on the Significant Relationship between Abstracting and Information Management In 21st Century.

Group	Mean \bar{X}	Std. Dev.	N	Df	Std. Error	P	T-cal. value	T-tab. value	Decision
Females	4.81	0.40	24	30	0.20	0.05	2.30	1.96	Ho Rejected
Males	4.35	0.51	8						

Field Survey, 2022

Table 6 presents the statistical analysis results to determine the relationship between abstracting and information management in the 21st century. The table includes the calculated T-value, the table T-value, the alpha level of significance ($P < 0.05$), and the degree of freedom (30). The calculated T-value is 2.30, while the table T-value is 1.96. With an alpha level of significance of $P < 0.05$ and a degree of freedom of 30, the calculated T-value is higher than the table T-value. As a result, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, based on the findings presented in Table 6, it can be concluded that there is a significant relationship between abstracting and information management in the 21st century. This implies that abstracting is requisite in information organization in 21st-century libraries.

Discussion of Findings

The first hypothesis looked at the connection between information management and classification. The findings indicated a strong correlation between classification and information management. This result is consistent with the definition of a classification scheme given by Nnadozie (2007), as reported by Atanda and Adeyemi (2018), who stated that a classification scheme is a system designed to divide the body of human knowledge into wide categories and specific issues. Classification schemes were created to help libraries organize knowledge so that papers could be quickly located, recognized, and retrieved for later use. The second hypothesis investigated the connection between bibliographic control and information management. The results showed a strong correlation between information management and bibliographic control. This result supports the claim stated by Amaraweera, (2010) that

bibliography is an essential resource for information retrieval in libraries. It is a list of articles, books, or shorter works that can be used to locate sources of information. Finding more works by a certain author or works on specific subjects would be difficult without bibliographies. The third hypothesis investigated how information management and abstracting are related. The findings showed a strong correlation between information management and abstracting. This result is in line with the viewpoint put forward by Atanda and Adeyemi (2018), who defined abstracting as the act of condensing a document into a manageable summary that incorporates important components such as the goals, scope, methodology, results, and suggestions. This procedure is essential for efficiently handling information since it offers a concise summary of the contents of a document.

Recommendations

Drawing from the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Resource centres should prioritize the tenacious maintenance of information organization methods such as classification.
2. The importance of bibliographic control in information organization should be recognized, encouraged, and taken seriously.
3. Given its significance in information management, continuous attention and focus should be dedicated to abstracting.

References

- Abata-Ebire, B. D., Adebowale, J. A., & Ojokuku, B. Y. (2018). Achieving sustainable development goals in Nigeria: The roles of libraries. *International Journal of Applied Technologies in Library and Information Management*, 4(2), 89-95.
- Atanda, L. A. & Adeyemi, S. A. (2018). Information retrieval tools, to accessing library resources. *Research Journal of Library and Information Science*, 2(2), 30-35.
- Ashikuzzaman, M. D. (2024). Abstracting Service. https://www.lisedunetwork.com/abstracting-service/#google_vignette
- Choo, C.W. (1998). Information management for intelligent organizations: the art of scanning the environment. Medford, NJ: Information Today, Inc.
- Emezie, N. A. & Nwaohiri, N. M. (2013). 21st century librarians and effective information service delivery. *Journal of Information and Knowledge Management*, 4(1), 30-43.
- Idachaba, J. A., Vehe, E. T., Tyonun, N. M., & Columbus, U. C.L.N. (2021). Organization and preservation of government publications in Benue State Legislative Library, Makurdi. *International Journal of Academic Library and Information Science*, 9(7), 364-370, July, <https://doi.org/10.14662/ijalis2021304>

- Joudrey, Daniel N., and Arlene G. Taylor (2018). *The Organization of Information*, 4th ed. Santa Barbara, CA: [Libraries Unlimited](#), 2018, [.ISBN 9781598848595 OCLC 1005741949](#)
- Lazarus, G. N., Adesoji, A. A., & Jinadu, I. (2019). Leadership and management practices in the 21st century academic libraries. *Journal of Library Services and Technologies*, 1(2), 51 – 61.
- Mastura, I. & Norhayati, J. (2017). Fundamentals of information management in organisation academic writing. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 7(12), 3-5.
- Muhammad, J. S., Azman Mat Isa, A. M., Samsudin, A. Z. H., & Miah, S. J. (2020). Critical factors for implementing effective information governance in Nigerian universities: A case study investigation. *Education and Information Technologies*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-020-10206-3>.
- Rifaudeen, M. M. (2015). Information Management in Libraries and Its Impact on Sustainable Library and Information Services with Special Reference to University Libraries of Sri Lanka
- Rowley, J. (1998). "Towards a framework for information management". *International Journal of Information Management*, 18 (5), 359-369.
- Radon, Rosemary (1996). "What Information? What Dynamics," *Information Dynamics*. Edited by Rosemary Radon. Cambridge, Eng.: Gower.
- Quora (2022) What is information organisation? <https://www.quora.com/What-is-involved-in-the-organization-of-information#:~:text=The%20organization%20of%20information%20involves,understanding%2C%20retrieval%2C%20and%20use>.
- Vijayakumar, A. & Vijayan, S. S. (2011). Application of information technology in libraries: An overview. *International Journal of Digital Library Services*, 1(2), 144-152.